

3D-printed micro-optical dark-field condenser: supplement

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1. IMAGES OF THE 3D-PRINTED ANNULAR APERTURE

Fig. S1. Three transmission microscope images of the 3D-printed annular aperture at different magnifications. Imaged with Keyence VHX-6000.

2. IMAGING SETUP DETAILS

The home-built imaging setup is based on the setups previously utilized in [1, 2]. Collimated white LED light (Thorlabs MCWHL P1 and Thorlabs SM1U25-A) first strikes a diffuser (Thorlabs DG10-1500-A) and then strikes the 3D-printed condenser, aperture side first. The light is spatially filtered by the annular IP-Superblack aperture and subsequently focused by the IPX-Clear lens, striking a sample. As samples, we illuminate a USAF 1951 resolution test chart (EdmundOptics 2" x 2" Positive, USAF 1951 Resolution Target), gold nanodisks as well as a sample with unstained onion cells. The samples are imaged with a basic imaging setup consisting of a 20x magnification, 0.42 NA microscope objective (Mitutoyo M Plan Apo 20x, part number 378-804-3), a tube lens (Mitutoyo MT-4 Accessory Tube Lens) and a camera (iDS UI-3180CP-C-HQ R2.1). An iris (Thorlabs SM1D12C) is placed between the objective and the tube lens in order to manually lower the NA to below that of the 3D-printed condenser (The 3D-printed condenser has a minimal NA of $NA_{\min, \text{condenser}} \approx 0.39$). For the illumination for Figures 2, 3, and 4, the full power of the light source (Thorlabs MCWHL P1) of 2350 mW was utilized. Brightness of the image was adjusted with the gain and exposure time of the camera (iDS UI-3180CP-C-HQ R2.1).

3. INTENSITY PROFILE COMPARISON OF THE DIFFERENT CONDENSER TYPES, COMMERCIAL DARK-FIELD, AND BRIGHT-FIELD CONDENSERS

We compare the performance of the miniaturized 3D-printed dark-field condenser with a commercial transmission dark-field microscope. Here, we use a Nikon Eclipse LV100ND transmission microscope equipped with a dark-field condenser (Nikon Dark Field Condenser, Dry, NA 0.95-0.80), a 20x magnification, NA 0.45 objective (Nikon, TU Plan Fluor, 20x/0.45, OFN25, WD4.5), and a Nikon DS-Fi3 CMOS camera. In addition, the same transmission microscope is used with a bright-field condenser (Nikon Bright Field Condenser, Dry, NA 0.4). The imaging 20x magnification objective has a similar NA of 0.45 in comparison to the home-built setup with a 20x magnification and an NA of 0.42 (reduced to below the NA of the 3D-printed dark-field condenser with a design of $NA_{\text{min,condenser}} \approx 0.39$ with an iris). The NA of the commercial dark-field condenser with 0.95-0.80 is a lot higher than the NA of the 3D-printed dark-field condenser with approximately 0.44-0.39 (maximum and minimum NA). The results prove that our 3D-printed condenser yields comparable contrast as the commercial dark-field condenser.

Fig. S2. Intensity profile comparison of group 6 of a positive USAF 1951 test chart with the plot on the right showing the normalized intensity along the red line in the left image. The test chart is imaged with (a) the 3D-printed IP-Superblack DF condenser, (b) the chromium aperture condenser, (c) collimated illumination without any condenser, (d) a commercial BF condenser, and (e) a commercial DF condenser.

Fig. S3. Intensity profile comparison of group 7 of a positive USAF 1951 test chart with the plot on the right indicating the normalized intensity along the red line in the left image. The test chart is imaged with (a) the 3D-printed IP-Superblack DF condenser, (b) the chromium aperture condenser, (c) collimated illumination without any condenser, (d) a commercial BF condenser, and (e) a commercial DF condenser.

4. COMPARISON OF GOLD NANODISK AND ONION IMAGING TO COMMERCIAL DARK-FIELD AND BRIGHT-FIELD CONDENSERS

Fig. S4. Comparison of BF and DF images of gold nanodisk structures forming a Lissajou pattern in (a)-(c), and a spiral structures in (d)-(f). Imaging is performed with the 3D-printed IP-Superblack DF condenser in (a) and (d), with a commercial DF condenser in (b) and (e), and with a commercial BF condenser in (c) and (f).

Fig. S5. Comparison of BF and DF images of onion cells. The cells are imaged with the 3D-printed DF condenser in (a), with the 3D-printed IP-Superblack DF condenser in (b), and with a commercial BF condenser in (c).

5. INTENSITY PROFILE COMPARISON OF GOLD NANODISK IMAGING

Fig. S6. Intensity profile comparison of imaged gold nanodisks forming a Lissajous pattern. The plot on the right depicts the normalized intensity along the red line in the left image. The nanodisks were imaged with the 3D-printed DF condenser on (a), and with collimated illumination with no condenser in (b).

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